

RISK MANAGEMENT AND BUSINESS INSURANCE

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Abstract. *This article examines the main areas of insurance regulation in the area of risk and hazard prevention in business activities. It is noted that an insurance company's pricing policy should reflect expected trends in the development of risks and hazards, which are reflected in innovations introduced in technologies, materials, building designs, structures, machinery, and mechanisms. The main types of insurance risks, along with explanations and descriptions using formulas, are also presented.*

Keywords: *insurance activities, pricing policy, insurance risks, entrepreneurial risk, insurance principles, risk prevention, insurance relations, risk management.*

Business activity is directly linked to risk. Entrepreneurs take risks throughout their entire career. But contrary to popular belief, risks in business are just as necessary as profit. Without them, entrepreneurship, as a tool for economic development, cannot fulfill its functions. Risks mediate the so-called "natural selection" among those who wish to become successful businessmen. Without them, it is impossible to imagine anything other than chaos in the entrepreneurial environment. Without risks, business will lose its significance and cease to be a source of profit, which will adversely affect the country's economy. Therefore, in economic activity, the strongest must survive.

The word "risk" is of Spanish-Portuguese origin and means "underwater rock," i.e., danger. Risk is understood as "playing on luck, in the hope of a happy outcome." Risk is an activity associated with overcoming uncertainty in a situation of inevitable choice, during which it is possible to quantitatively and qualitatively assess the probability of achieving the intended result, failure, and deviation from the goal.

There are objective causes and factors that influence the emergence of risks. The basis for the emergence of risk is entrepreneurial uncertainty.

As a rule, beginning entrepreneurs are most susceptible to risk. Lack of experience, knowledge, and connections—all of these inevitably play a role in natural selection. Typically, risks at the beginning of an entrepreneur's activity are outlined in the business plan, and the ways to address them should also be indicated.

The purpose of this work is to clarify the concept of risk in business. To achieve this goal, the following objectives were completed:

- clarify the concept and essence of risk;
- list the main characteristics of risk;
- provide a classification of risks in business;
- highlight methods for mitigating business risks.

The problem of risk is one of the key concepts in financial and industrial activity. It is particularly important in entrepreneurial activity. Risk acts as an incentive for the efficient use of capital. In global practice, entrepreneurial activity is defined as the proactive, independent activity of individuals and their associations, aimed at generating profit, carried out at their own risk and under their own financial responsibility. As a result, risk has acquired a more important, independent meaning, both in theory and in management practice.

Modern business is unthinkable without risk, as success depends not only on the correctness and soundness of the chosen entrepreneurial strategy but also on considering the likelihood of critical situations. To survive in a market economy, one must embrace technological innovation and take bold, decisive action, which increases risk. Therefore, the primary tasks of an entrepreneur are the ability to assess and manage risk, rather than simply avoid it.

There are a wide variety of opinions regarding the definition, essence, and nature of risk. This is due to the multifaceted nature of this phenomenon, its insufficient use in real-life activities, and its neglect in existing legislation. Let's consider two basic concepts that complement each other and encompass the general nature of risk.

The first definition defines risk as the probability (threat) of an enterprise losing some of its resources, losing revenue, or incurring additional expenses as a result of certain production and financial activities. Consequently, risk refers to the possibility of an adverse event, the possibility of failure, or the possibility of danger.

The second definition of risk is directly related to the concept of a "risk situation." A situation, in general, is a combination or set of various circumstances and conditions that create a specific environment for a particular activity. This environment can facilitate or hinder the implementation of a given action. In a risk situation, it is possible to quantitatively and qualitatively determine the probability of a particular option, and three conditions accompany it:

- the presence of uncertainty;
- the need to choose an alternative (including rejecting a choice);
- the ability to assess the likelihood of the chosen alternatives being realized.

A risk situation is qualitatively different from a situation of uncertainty. In a situation of uncertainty, the probability of the outcomes of decisions or events is fundamentally undetermined. Consequently, a risk situation is a type of uncertainty situation, since the occurrence of events is probable and can be determined.

By its nature, risk is divided into three types:

1. When a subject choosing from several alternatives has objective probabilities of achieving the expected outcome. These probabilities are independent of the firm's immediate influence: inflation, competition, statistical studies, environmental conditions, etc.

2. When the probabilities of the expected outcome can only be determined based on subjective assessments, i.e., the subject is dealing with subjective probabilities. Subjective probabilities directly characterize the firm's performance: production potential, level of subject and technological specialization, labor organization, etc.

3. When a subject, in the process of selecting and implementing an alternative, has both objective and subjective probabilities. These risk modifications enable the subject to make a choice and strive to implement it. As a result, risk exists both at the decision-making stage and at the implementation stage.

Based on these conditions, the second definition of risk is as follows. Risk is an action (deed, act) performed under conditions of choice (in a situation of choice in the hope of a favorable outcome), where failure poses the possibility (degree of danger) of ending up in a worse position than before the choice (than in the case of not taking the action). Risk is more fully defined as an activity associated with overcoming uncertainty in a situation of inevitable choice, during which it is possible to quantitatively and qualitatively assess the likelihood of achieving the intended result, failure, and deviation from the goal. From this latter definition, we can identify the key elements that will form the essence of the concept of "risk":

1. The possibility of deviation from the intended goal for which the chosen alternative was pursued (both negative and positive deviations).
2. The likelihood of achieving the desired result.
3. Lack of confidence in achieving the goal.
4. The possibility of material, moral, and other losses associated with implementing the alternative chosen under conditions of uncertainty.

Risk should not be avoided, but if a decision is made to take a risk, it should be carefully forecast beforehand and, when implementing the planned measures, adhere to the project's established framework. Accepting a risk-related project requires identifying and comparing potential losses and gains. If risk is not supported by calculations, it will most likely end in failure and be accompanied by certain losses.

The main characteristics of risk are: inconsistency, alternativeness, and uncertainty. Inconsistency in risk leads to a clash between objectively existing risky actions and their subjective assessment. Alongside initiatives, innovative ideas, and the introduction of new promising activities that accelerate technological progress and influence public opinion and the spiritual atmosphere of society, there also exists conservatism, dogmatism, subjectivism, and so on.

Alternatives presuppose the need to choose from two or more possible solutions, directions, and actions. Without the possibility of choice, a risky situation does not arise, and therefore, no risk exists.

Uncertainty is defined as the incompleteness or imprecision of information about the conditions for implementing a project (decision). The existence of risk is directly related to the presence of uncertainty, which is heterogeneous in both form and content. Entrepreneurial activity is influenced by the uncertainty of the external environment (economic, political, social, etc.), a multitude of variables, counterparties, and individuals whose behavior cannot always be predicted with acceptable accuracy.

Classification of business risks. Let's first consider external risks beyond the entrepreneur's control.

Country risk is a risk directly related to the internationalization of business activities. It depends on the political and economic stability of the countries—importers and exporters. Causes of country risk may include instability of government, peculiarities of the state structure and legislation, ineffective economic policies pursued by the government, ethnic and regional issues, sharp polarization of interests between different social groups, etc.

Currency risks are risks associated with changes in exchange rates.

The magnitude of currency risk is associated with the loss of purchasing power of the currency, and therefore it is directly dependent on the time lag between the transaction date and the payment date. An exporter incurs exchange rate losses if a contract is concluded before the exchange rate of the payment currency has fallen, because the exporter receives less national currency for the proceeds. An importer, on the other hand, incurs losses if the exchange rate rises, since purchasing it requires spending more national currency. Tax risks are considered from two perspectives: the entrepreneur's and the government's. The entrepreneur's tax risk is associated with possible changes in tax policy (the introduction of new taxes, the elimination or reduction of tax breaks, etc.), as well as changes in tax rates. The government's tax risk consists of a possible reduction in budget revenues as a result of changes in tax policy and/or tax rates.

Force majeure risk is the risk of natural disasters (floods, earthquakes, storms, and other climatic cataclysms), wars, revolutions, coups, strikes, etc., that interfere with the entrepreneur's operations. Losses caused by force majeure are typically compensated through transaction insurance with specialized insurance companies.

Internal risks, unlike external ones, are largely determined by erroneous decisions made by the entrepreneur due to their incompetence.

Organizational risk is a risk caused by deficiencies in work organization. The main causes of organizational risk are:

- a) poor organization:
 - planning and design errors;
 - weak regulation;
 - errors in personnel selection and placement, etc.;
- b) marketing deficiencies:
 - incorrect product selection (no sales);
 - low-quality goods;
 - incorrect market selection, etc.;
- c) unstable financial situation.

The main causes of resource risk are:

- lack of resource safety margin in the event of a changing situation;

- labor shortage;
- material shortage;
- supply disruptions;
- product shortages.

If a company or individual entrepreneur has available funds, they face the difficult task of determining the size and scope of investments. An investor's portfolio is the collection of securities they hold. Portfolio risk is the probability of loss on individual types of securities, as well as on the entire category of loans. To create a securities portfolio, it's sufficient to invest in a single type of financial asset. However, by investing in the shares of a single company, the investor becomes dependent on fluctuations in its market value. If they invest their capital in the shares of several companies, their performance will, of course, also depend on exchange rate fluctuations, but not on individual exchange rates, but on the average. The average exchange rate, however, typically fluctuates less, since an increase in the price of one security may cause the price of another to decline, and the fluctuations can cancel each other out. Such a portfolio with a variety of securities is called diversified. It significantly reduces diversification (unsystematic) risk, which is determined by factors specific to a given investor. Along with diversification risk, there is non-diversification (systematic) risk, which cannot be reduced through diversification. Credit risk (default risk) is the risk of a borrower's failure to repay the principal and interest on the loan in accordance with the terms and conditions of the loan agreement. Innovation risk is the risk associated with the financing and application of scientific and technological innovations.

The most common, widely used, and effective methods of risk prevention and mitigation are: insurance, reserve funds, diversification, and limitation.

Insurance is one of the most common methods of risk mitigation. The essence of insurance is the transfer of risk (responsibility for negative consequences) to someone else for a certain fee, i.e., the distribution of damages between the insured parties. Insurance can be personal, property, or liability insurance. In the system of economic risk insurance, property insurance and liability insurance are predominantly used. Property insurance is a branch of insurance in which the object of insurance relations is property in various forms (buildings, equipment, vehicles, raw materials, materials, products, livestock, agricultural land, etc.) and property interests. Most often, property is insured against destruction or damage as a result of natural disasters, accidents, fires, illness, theft, etc. In recent years, liability insurance has become increasingly common in business activities. Liability insurance is a branch of insurance in which the object is liability to third parties for damage caused to them as a result of any action or inaction of the policyholder. An entrepreneur's liability encompasses a wide range of situations, from liability for loan defaults to liability for environmental pollution and damage to nature and residents of the area due to improper business practices.

Reserving funds (self-insurance), as a way to reduce the negative consequences of risky events, involves an entrepreneur creating separate loss compensation funds using a portion of their own working capital. Typically, entrepreneurs choose this risk mitigation method when they believe the cost of reserve funds is less than the cost of insurance premiums. Diversification plays an important role in risk mitigation measures.

Diversification is the process of distributing invested funds among different, unrelated investment objects. Most literature views diversification as an effective way to reduce risks in portfolio management. However, this method has a much broader scope of effective application and can be used in various business sectors, including industrial production, construction, trade, and others. In the insurance business, an example of diversification is expanding the insurance coverage. For example, insuring crops, buildings, etc., over a small area (in the event of a hurricane, etc.) can lead to the need to pay out larger insurance premiums. Increasing the insurance coverage reduces the likelihood of a simultaneous insured event. Diversification is a way to reduce unsystematic risk. Diversification cannot reduce systematic risk, which is determined by the general state of the economy and is associated with factors such as war, inflation, global changes in monetary policy, etc.

Limitation is the establishment of a system of restrictions, both upper and lower, that helps reduce the degree of risk. In business, limits are most often applied to selling goods on credit, providing loans, determining capital investment amounts, and so on. This primarily applies to monetary funds—setting maximum amounts of expenses, credit, investments, and so on. An example of a limit is setting a maximum amount (cap) that an insurer can retain. Exceeding this amount entails the refusal of insurance or the use of forms such as coinsurance or reinsurance.

Acquiring complete information is also one way to reduce risk. With more accessible information, consumers can make better forecasts and reduce risk. Given that information is a valuable commodity, people are willing to pay for it. In practice, the most effective results can only be achieved through the integrated use of various risk mitigation methods. By combining them in various combinations, an optimal balance can be achieved between the level of risk reduction achieved and the additional costs required to achieve it.

LITERATURE

1. Урунбаева, Н. А. Развитие устойчивого механизма управления водопользования в условиях орошаемого земледелия в зарубежных странах / Н. А. Урунбаева, Д. Б. Халифазода // Финансово-экономический вестник. – 2021. – № S4.2(29). – С. 75-85. – EDN QYQKNW.
2. Давлатзода, Қ. Қ. Тальрибаи хориљӣ оид ба ташаккул ва рушди кластерҳои агросаноатӣ дар минтақа / Қ. Қ. Давлатзода, Қ. Б. Халифазода // Политехнический вестник. Серия: Интеллект. Инновации. Инвестиции. – 2021. – No. 3(55). – P. 88-93. – EDN VCBOLL.
3. Шералиев, Э. Н. Фаъолгардонии ҷалби сармояҳо ба рушди кластерҳои Пахтакорӣ дар минтақа / Э. Н. Шералиев, Қ. Б. Халифазода // Идоракунии давлатӣ. – 2022. – No. 4-1(58). – P. 116-123. – EDN DFOCDC.
4. Давлатзода, К. К. Ташаккул ва инкишофи кластерҳои соҳавӣ дар минтақа / К. К. Давлатзода, Д. Халифазода. – Душанбе : Таджикский национальный университет, 2023. – 158 p. – EDN DGVUAF.
5. Хусайнов, М. С. Роҳҳои афзалиятноки рушди бозори суғурта дар Ҷумҳурии Тоҷикистон / М. С. Хусайнов, Қ. Б. Халифазода // Идоракунии давлатӣ. – 2024. – No. 4-3(71). – P. 234-242. – EDN VOZEZM.
6. Халифазода, Д. Б. Механизмы государственного регулирования развития рынка страховых услуг в Республике Таджикистан / Д. Б. Халифазода // Государственное управление. – 2024. – № 4-3(71). – С. 195-202. – EDN BDIRVZ.
7. Халифазода, Д. Б. Инвестиции как основное средство формирования промышленно-отраслевых кластеров Хатлонского региона / Д. Б. Халифазода // Государственное управление. – 2024. – № 4-1(69). – С. 224-233. – EDN MSJFSA.
8. Абдумухторозода, Н. А. Масъалаҳои назариявии шуғли аҳоли ва роҳҳои идораи он / Н. А. Абдумухторозода, Қ. Б. Халифазода // Паёми Донишгоҳи миллии Тоҷикистон. Бахши илмҳои иҷтимоӣ-иқтисодӣ ва ҷамъиятӣ. – 2024. – No. 7. – P. 141-146. – EDN JKAFPN.
9. Муминзода, А. Мавқеи суғурта дар сохтори институтсионалии иқтисодиёт / А. Муминзода, Қ. Б. Халифазода // Мақомоти гумрук ва нақши он дар таъмини бехатарии иқтисодӣ : Сборник материалов международной научно-практической конференции, Душанбе, 30 ноября 2024 года. – Душанбе: ДДМИТ, Донишгоҳи давлатии молия ва иқтисоди Тоҷикистон, 2024. – P. 140-144. – EDN KJXFOZ.
10. Халифазода, Д. Б. Налогообложение деятельности страховых компаний / Д. Б. Халифазода // Государственное управление. – 2025. – № 1(72). – С. 187-194. – EDN DLJAYJ.